

LANGUAGE CHOICE DURING ARGUMENTS IN MULTILINGUAL SPEAKERS

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This article examines how multilingual individuals strategically select or switch languages in emotionally charged conflicts. Drawing on previous research in sociolinguistics, pragmatics and bilingualism, it can be seen that language choice in arguments is not random but influenced by emotional intensity, cultural norms and communicative context. Multilingual individuals often switch to a language that allows them to express emotions more accurately or distance themselves emotionally. Furthermore, cultural background plays a crucial role in shaping communication styles, levels of directness, and conflict resolution strategies. Understanding language choice during arguments contributes to broader research on multilingualism, identity and cross-cultural communication.

In modern linguistics, multilingualism is studied not only as a cognitive ability but also as evolving form of communication shaped by social interactions. Argumentative discourse offers context for observing multilingual practices where emotional tension and interpersonal dynamics emphasized. Because arguments demand quick responses, speakers must react rapidly which makes their choice of language meaningful.

Scholars findings suggest that multilingual speakers frequently switch languages during conflict situations due to emotional, social and pragmatic reasons. This article explores how and why such language choices occur and demonstrates that second language is often limited by both emotional depth and cognitive factors.

As observed by Fishman J.A. language choice among multilingual speakers is closely connected to social context rather than randomness. He notes that "*language choice is not random; it is determined by who speaks what language to whom and when*"¹

According to this statement speakers choose language depending on their relationship with the interlocutor, context and purpose of the interaction. From this standpoint language use in arguments should be understood as a socially driven choice rather than and individual preference. This discovery gives us a theoretical foundation for language choice during conflicts. Speakers may switch to a language which is socially dominant in order to establish authority and seriousness during the arguments.

For instance:

Uzbek: "*Nima uchun kech keldingiz?*"

Russian: "*Объясните, пожалуйста, причину вашего опоздания.*"

In this example authority and distance showed through the usage of Russian. Seriousness and control conveyed by the speaker during the argument with the help of formal manner.

When people switch language mostly it can show how they feel, how serious or casual they are and what emotions they are feeling and how they see the person they are talking. Likewise, Gumperz John noted that

¹ Fishman J.A. Sociolinguistics: A Brief Introduction. Rowley, MA: Newbury House Publishers, 1972. –P. 20.

Code switching has pragmatic purpose apart from linguistic ones. He writes : "Code-switching is often used to mark emotional involvement or a change in conversational footing."²

This claim emphasizes how language switching usually signals a shift in the speaker's emotional state or attitude toward interaction. In argumentative discourse, such changes indicate how the person is feeling like getting angry, excited or upset. At the same time it may signal a shift in the attitude toward the person they are talking to. For instance, depending on situation speaker might become more serious, bold or even distant. Furthermore, Gumperz points out that when emotions too strong people often change to their first language. "Switches frequently occur at points of heightened emotional tension."³

This means when people feel very emotional such as angry, frustrated or upset they are more likely to change from one language to another. During these moments especially moments of disagreement, speakers try to use language which is best for expressing feelings and for sure it is their first, native language.

For instance:

Context: Two bilingual speakers (Uzbek-Russian) are arguing about a broken agreement.

Uzbek (calm discussion stage):

"Bu masalani tinch yo'l bilan hal qilaylik."

(Let's resolve this issue peacefully.)

Uzbek (disagreement increases):

"Sen va'da bergan eding."

Switch to Russian (emotional escalation):

"Ты всегда так делаешь! Это уже надоело!"

(You always do this! I'm tired of it!)

In the example above, the interaction begins in Uzbek reflecting regulated communication. However, as emotional intensity increases, the speaker switches to Russian at the peak of frustration. This shift corresponds to Gumperz describes as language switches occurring at points of heightened emotional tension.

While Gumperz focus on how emotions and interactions cause individuals switch language but language switching also shows social purpose. It means language helps people manage their social role and relationships. Heller .M noted that "Code-switching can be seen as a resource for the construction, negotiation, and maintenance of social identities in interaction."⁴

From this view it can be understood that by choosing one language over another speakers can create or maintain their social identity because identity becomes crucial in argumentative discourse. Switching to their native language allows them to create and establish authority, seriousness or even closeness. In simple words it shows who they are, how serious they are or even how close they feel to other person.

The relationship between emotional expression and dominance of first language is widely discussed by Aneta Pavlenko. She explains that emotional power of first language rooted back

² Gumperz J.J Discourse Strategies. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1982, P. –77.

³ Gumperz J.J Discourse Strategies. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1982, P. –78.

⁴ Heller M. Codeswitching: Anthropological and sociolinguistic perspectives. Berlin,1988. P.-23.

in early childhood. She writes : *"For many bilinguals, the first language remains the language of emotions, because it is the language in which early affective socialization took place."*⁵

From this view we can understand that early childhood experiences, such as expressions of love, punishment, comfort and conflict are first experienced and typically encoded in first language. As a result, emotional expressions in L1 often feel more sincere, authentic and intense than those expressed in later learned language. When emotional tension increased during the argument, multilingual speakers may switch to their first language because it allows them express anger, frustration or hurt more powerfully.

For instance:

Calm stage (English – L2):

"I don't think you understand how I feel."

Emotional escalation (switch to Uzbek – L1):

"Sen meni umuman tushunmaysan!

Boshqa bu mavzuda tortishishni soxlamayman!"

In this conversation at the beginning speaker tries to maintain control over the discussion, however when pressure intensifies speaker immediately abandons this language and changes it into native one. From this example it is obvious that switch is not random and provides explanation for language choice during arguments among multilingual speakers.

In addition, Pavlenko Aneta states that *"Strong emotions such as anger are more difficult to express in a second language."*⁶

This statement provides support for the claim that multilingual speakers often experience limitations when they want to express emotions in their second language. Because a second language lacks emotional depth and instinctive control as the first language and speakers may struggle to express themselves fully. For this reason they often return to their native language during conflicts where emotional expression feels more natural.

The role of speaker intention in language choice is clearly explained by Geoffrey Leech in his influential work. Leech emphasizes how interpersonal factors influence language use, stating that *"the choice of linguistic form depends on the speaker's communicative intention and social relationship with the hearer"*⁷

During arguments speakers do not simply select words to convey propositional meaning, they choose words that represent their desired attitude, emotional involvement and the level of social distance. As speakers may switch languages to align more effectively with their communicative goals in order to establish authority, express dissatisfaction, mitigate conflict or preserve social harmony. Leech's approach offers a valuable theoretical foundation for understanding language choice during arguments as a strategic and intention-driven process.

Taken together, these viewpoints reveal that language switching during conflicts serves multiple pragmatic purposes. It enhances emotional expressiveness, can create psychological distance, establish authority or align with culturally appropriate norms.

Understanding language choice in argumentative discourse contributes to broader research on identity formation, multilingual interaction and cross-cultural communication.

⁵ Pavlenko A. *Emotions and multilingualism*. Cambridge:Cambridge University Press, 2005. P.-155.

⁶ Pavlenko A. *Emotions and multilingualism*. Cambridge:Cambridge University Press, 2005. P.-155.

⁷ Leech G. *Principles of Pragmatics*. London: Longman, 1983. -P.82

Additionally, it has practical implications for conflict resolution and language education where awareness of emotional and cultural dimensions of language can promote more effective and empathetic communication.

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